

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B174
Date: 15 Feb 2006
Take Off: 09:44:00
Landing: 14:31:54
Flight Time: 4h47m54s

Campaign: DODO
Trials Instructions: Biomass / Aerosol Sampling
Operating Area: North of Dakar for source, south for advection

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Simon Osborne	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	VACC/PAN/WAS	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
7	AVAPS/ccm2/CCN/CVI	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Claire McConnell	Reading University
10	Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
11	Core Chemistry	Alan Woolley	FAAM
12	SWS/SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
13	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 2/AMS	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B174 Track 15-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b174

Date: 15 Feb 2006

Project: DODO

Location: North of Dakar for dust sources, south for advection

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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093058		inu to nav	0.04 kft	343	
093104		engine start	0.04 kft	343	
093319		power change	0.04 kft	343	
093509		tapes start	0.04 kft	343	
093518		taxy start	0.04 kft	343	
093653		asp open	0.05 kft	106	
094400		T/O	0.03 kft	353	P1 true start
094417	100011	Profile 1	0.23 - 13.0 kft	354	
094923		nevzorov zero	2.7 kft	027	
095023		Profile 1	3.3 kft	027	1000ft/min roc
100157		sonde 1	13.0 kft	021	launch
100324	102118	Profile 2	13.0 - -.01 kft	021	
102118	102945	Profile 3	-.01 - 4.9 kft	047	
103704	104102	Profile 4	5.0 - 3.0 kft	005	
103841		Profile 4	4.0 kft	003	rod 500ft/min
104303	104532	Profile 5	3.0 - 4.5 kft	163	
104533	110016	Run 1	4.5 kft	164	
111038	120553	Run 2	22.0 kft	216	
120554	123323	Profile 6	22.0 - 0.07 kft	177	qnh 1013
121329		sonde 2	14.7 kft	172	launch
123323	123425	Profile 7	0.07 - 0.50 kft	279	qnh 1013
123425	124011	Run 3.1	0.50 - 0.53 kft	277	
124225	130004	Run 3.2	0.55 - 0.62 kft	093	
130241	131459	Run 4.1	0.17 - 0.16 kft	282	
131612	132339	Run 4.2	0.15 - 0.20 kft	047	
132457	132906	Run 4.3	0.14 - 0.25 kft	291	
133032	133536	Run 4.4	0.17 - 0.18 kft	052	
133653	134305	Run 4.5	0.18 kft	290	
134347	135718	Profile 8	0.16 - 13.0 kft	345	
135734		sonde 3	13.0 kft	353	launch
135954	140213	Profile 9	13.0 - 15.0 kft	352	
143154		Land	0.08 kft	354	at Dakar
143927		standstill	0.10 kft	335	14'44.60N. 17'29.45W

B174 Track 15-FEB-06

GOOY → GQNN - Overview

NavData Cycle 2006-1 Expires: Thursday, 16 February 2006.

Scale: 1:3077046 (1 inch = 42.20 naut mi). Printed on 14 Feb 2006

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.150

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO Flight: In situ dust sampling from Western Sahara sources revisiting plume sampled in B173

Flight No: B174

Date: 15th February 2006

Objectives:

1. In-situ sampling of Saharan dust outflow over the ocean.
2. Assessing size and extent of plume identified in B174
3. Possible characterisation of surface radiative properties and radiation measurement from above dust layers.

Location: Over ocean North of Dakar, and across Western parts of Mauritania.

BIKIS: 16 17N 16 47'W

NOUAKCHOTT: 18 05N 15 57'W

GUPEL 21 20N 15 0'W

DAKAR: 14 45N 17 28'W

Weather: ideally clear skies, possible cirrus over region, most likely to south

Special requirements: drop-sondes over ocean north of Dakar.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar. Open air sample pipes on runway.
2. Profile ascent to FL120 on a heading towards BIKIS, 500ft/min below 3000ft, 1000ft/min above 3000ft. Prepare for dropsonde launch during ascent and drop at the top of the profile [20 mins, T=20 mins].
3. Profile descent from FL120 to 50ft at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft/min below 3000ft [15 mins, T=35 mins].
4. Head to GUPEL via NOUAKCHOTT, performing one sawtooth from MPA to above the dust layer at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft/min below 3000ft (suggest FL060) [20mins, T=55 mins].
5. Profile ascent to FL120 on a heading towards GUPEL, 500ft/min below 3000ft, 1000ft/min above 3000ft. Prepare for dropsonde launch during ascent and drop at the top of the profile [20 mins, T=75 mins].
6. Profile descent to GUPEL from FL120 to 50ft at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft/min below 3000ft [15 mins, T=90 mins].
7. Conduct 4 cross wind SLRs for 15 mins at various distances along the 33° DAKAR radial once at MPA and once at an altitude in the plume determined from the sawtooths (suggest 2000'). Zigzag performed to connect SLRs at low level. [210 mins, T=300 mins].
8. Land

Refuel

If clear skies and dust overhead in the region of Dakar:

9. Take off from Dakar. Open air sample pipes on runway.
10. Profile ascent to FL120 in direction of dust plume, 500ft/min below 3000ft, 1000ft/min above 3000ft. Prepare for dropsonde launch during ascent and drop at the top of the profile [20 mins, T=20 mins].
11. Profile descent to above dust layer (suggest FL050) at 1000 ft/min. [10 mins, T=30 mins]
12. Conduct a series of 4 orbits at maximum bank angle [10 mins, T=40 mins]
13. Profile descent at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and 500ft/min below 3000ft to 600 ft [10 mins, T= 50 mins].
14. Conduct a series of 4 orbits at maximum bank angle [10 mins, T=60 mins]
15. Profile ascent to FL120 in direction of dust plume, 500ft/min below 3000ft, 1000ft/min above 3000ft. Prepare for dropsonde launch during ascent and drop at the top of the profile [20 mins, T=80 mins].
16. Profile descent to land [20 mins, T=100 mins].

Flight B174

15th February 2006

Weather conditions:

Surface flow from NNE, advection of dust plume off the coast to the SSW. Still cirrus to the north of Dakar and medium level cloud over Dakar itself. Similar cloud to the south of Dakar, but some clear slots and more of these forecast during the day.

Summary of the flight:

A very successful flight DODO was conducted to sample the dust plume over the ocean that was first sampled nearer the sources in B173 i.e. after 24 hrs of further ageing. Taken together B173 and B174 will provide an excellent case study of dust short-scale evolution over the ocean and hence help satisfy three(?) of DODO's aims.

After take-off, an initial failed attempt was made to hunt for dust near the surface sources to the north of Dakar (like in B173). However, we found winds had died down from yesterday and visibility had increased to 6-10 km. Only light loadings of dust were found as we got as far as 18°N, 16°W before turning south. A 15 min SLR was made going south at 4500ft within light dust conditions (CCN, filters) before climbing to FL220 and zooming south at high speed to locate the B173 dust plume based on the B173 winds.

A profile descent was made into the new area from FL220 to 50ft. Multiple biomass burning aerosol layers were identified with tops at FL125. A peak in the PCASP concentration of 2600/cc was found at ~3600ft. A low-level layer of dust was successfully found below 2300ft down to the surface. A clear slot was at ~2600ft. A run was made roughly across-plume at 500ft. PCASP concs were ~400/cc. The PCASP size distribution showed less large particles than in B173 presumably due to sedimentation. A reciprocal run was made at 100ft still within the dust but low enough to enable radiation measurements to be made (some cirrus above though- use the upward facing camera to help). Wind speeds were less than 10 m/sec with little white-capping. The majority of aerosol at this height was thought to be dust. Green scatter coeffs were $\sim 300 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$. A good plume structure was identified during both these runs so that a series of zig-zags was made at 100ft on headings of $\sim 050^\circ$ and $\sim 290^\circ$ working "upstream". The plume was transected during each of these four runs. Cloud conditions improved during this low level work and some decent radiation measurements should be possible. A short period (~6 min) was made with ARIES and SWS looking in the nadir at 100ft; otherwise all views were true zenith. CO levels were slightly higher in the dust layer compared to the clear slot just above it. A final profile was carried out from 100ft to FL130 where multiple (at least three) biomass burning aerosol layers were seen with both instruments and the naked eye.

Sonde drops:

- (1) 100156 z on hdg 021 to the north of Dakar (top of P1 at FL130)
- (2) 121328 z on hdg 172 profiling into the operating area (during P6 at FL144)
- (3) 135736 z on hdg 353 profiling out of the operating area (top of P8 at FL130)

Mission Scientist's Log

AS = S. R. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.174**

Date **15/02/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0944	P1	P1			T/O DAKAR AIRFIELD. Some low cir over coast. Ci ahead v. hazy over coast & sea.
		2000ft			↳ P1ASP noise: sea salt?
		3000ft			↳ 1000 ft/min. Can see top of wind: noise?
100010	P1	P2130	021	15.6 17.0	End profile climb & hold for cate chem. & dropsonde.
100156	-	P2130	021	15.8 16.9	Dropsonde #1 go! can see low cir over sea & land to our right!
100323	P2	P2130	021	15.9 16.7	Start profile descent.
		4200'			Top of pollution: light dust?
					$\text{VSP} \approx 50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
		850'			Looking further to right over coast
		560'			SMK now. VSP increase: sea salt
102117	P2/P3	50'	042	16.9 16.4	End profile. Clearer of hours (SS4) P1ASP noise at base
		4900'			can see top of dust clearly.
102949		5000'			End profile climb & hold above desert
103703	P4	5000'	006	17.8 16.0	Start profile descent over coast.
104100	P4	3900'	003	18.0 16.0	End profile descent - ABANDON & turn south.
104300	P5	3000'	164	18.0 16.0	Start profile climb.
104531	P5/P1	4500'	104	17.8 16.0	End profile & start run along coast back to DAKAR
	P1				FILTERS & COOL GO!!
110016	P6	4500'	200	16.9 16.3	End run & zoom up to P220 for fast transit to south of DAKAR to hunt for dust. Clear above, but Ci ahead.
120551	P6	P220	172	11.9 16.9	Start profile towards point A looks hazy ahead.

Mission Scientist's Log

MS = D. R. OSBORNE

Flight No B.174.....

Date 15/02/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1208		FL200			broken ATCu above. cannot see any MBL cloud below. can see sea surface, but looks a little fuzzy.
					for too much cloud for radiometer work.
121328	P6	FL114	177	11.3 16.9	Soil # 2 release now.
		FL25			hit up of aerosol - BIOMASS?
		FL107			PCASP ~ 500/c
		FL80			PCASP ~ 1000/c! cont
		FL070			Bene of biomass? No.
		FL050			Low: more lens.
12235		6000'		10.7 16.6	Another bene of biomass
		3600'			PCASP ~ 2600/c!
		2600'			clear shot
		2300'			hit different aerosol: sea salt?
		1800'			into lowest layer - dust!
123523	P6	50'	228	10.4 16.9	End profile descent in dust
12401	R3.1	500'			Start run SD = 100-200 PCASP ~ 400/c
	R3.1	500'		10.5 17.3	end run in dust due to decreasing cond
124223	R3.2	500'	093	10.5 17.3	Start run. at Neph ~ 250 x 10 ⁶
130004	R3.2	500'	095	10.4 16.2	End run (cloud ahead) ⁺ droppin
130219	R3.3	100'	092	10.4 16.3	Start run low level.
					was part of Li done - at would get something for rad!!
131459	R3.3	100'	297	10.6 17.0	End run.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...174**

 Date **15/02/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131616	Rk-1	100'	048	10.7 17.0	Start run ^{Fig 7018} Some wisps of ci about - RADIOMETERS Sud - Resp. Sid ~ 150
					Too cloudy for ORBITS ^{Bumble} vis
132337	Rk-1	100'	032	11.0 16.7	End Run (out of range)
132457	Rk-2	100'	291	11.9 16.7	Start Run going across deep plume
132852	Rk-2	100'	289	11.1 16.9	End Run (change filters)
133030	Rk-3	100'	052	11.1 16.9	Start next run. ^{now} windy ^{westerly}
133534	Rk-3	100'	049	11.3 16.7	End Run → coincided with plume
133651	Rk-4	100'	290	11.3 16.7	Start Run, straight back into plume.
134303	Rk-4	100'	289	11.4 17.0	Start End Run (out of range)
134345	P8 ↑	1000'	345	11.3 17.0	Start profile climb.
					1000 ft in all the way
134532	P8 ↑	1600'			top of last (main layer) ?
134753		3800'			cloud dropping, but not sign
					still dusty.
		4500'			BROWN LAYER, only a few hundred feet
		5200'			Blue clear slot.
		6000'			Next BIOMASS layer.
		7500'			Next layer !!, cloudier to
135716	P8 →	FL 30	353	12.3 17.3	End profile, just at ^{the north.} top of aerosol
135836					Save # 3 now
135954	P9 ↑	FL 30	352	12.5 17.3	Start profile ascent to get the

tracks generally not on

140211 P9 → FL 150 352 12.7 17.3 End profile ascent. ^{clean air.}
 + End SCIENCE.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B174

Date : 15/02/06

Operator and contact info : Alan Woolley alwo@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	none
O₃	none
NO_x	None
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/a
WAS	N/A

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B174

Date: 15/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:44:17																Start Profile 1 from Take-off	
09:47:41	270	0.10	Off	10	1											FL020	
09:49:55	120	0.11	Off	15	1											FL030	
09:51:08	20	0.10	Off	2												FL040	
09:52:07	25	0.11	Off	2												FL050	
09:53:09	25	0.12	Off	1												FL060	
09:54:09	7	0.14	Off													FL070	
09:55:19	30	0.11	Off													FL080	
09:56:15	15	0.11	Off													FL090	
09:57:15	20	0.13	Off													FL100	
09:58:16	25	0.13	Off													FL110	
09:59:15	8	0.14	Off													FL120	
10:00:09	10	0.14	Off													End of Profile 1 @ FL130	
10:03:23	8	0.14	Off													Start Profile 2 from FL130	
10:06:44	4	0.14	Off													FL100	
10:07:50	5	0.12	Off													FL090	
10:09:08	25	0.14	Off													FL080	
10:10:12	7	0.15	Off													FL070	
10:11:07	Noise	0.13	Off													FL060	
10:12:17	Noise	0.14	Off													FL050	
10:13:20	230	0.11	Off	10	1											FL040	
10:14:32	220	0.11	Off	10	1											FL030	
10:16:36	280	0.11	Off	10	1											FL020	
10:18:36	290	0.11	Off	10	1											FL010	
10:21:16	520	0.11	Off	90	10											End of Profile 2 & Start Profile 3 from 50'	
10:23:45	240	0.11	Off	10	1											FL010	
10:25:40	250	0.11	Off	10	1											FL020	
10:27:16	210	0.11	Off	10	1											FL030	
10:29:00	210	0.12	Off	10	1											FL040	
10:29:45	180	0.11	Off	10	1											End of Profile 3 @ FL050	
10:37:04	170	0.11	Off	10	1											Start Profile 4 from FL050	
10:38:30	220	0.11	Off	10	1											FL040	
10:41:01	220	0.11	Off	10	2											End of Profile 4 @ FL030	
10:43:03	230	0.10	Off	10	1											Start Profile 5 from FL030	
10:45:30																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 1 @ FL045	
10:46:00	160	0.10	Off	10	1												
10:48:00	160	0.10	Off	10	1												
10:50:00	150	0.10	Off	10	1												
10:52:00	230	0.10	Off	10	1												
10:54:00	210	0.12	Off	10	1												
10:56:00	180	0.10	Off	10	1												
10:58:00	210	0.10	Off	10	1												
11:00:15																End of Run 1	
11:10:40																Start Run 2 @ FL220	
11:11:00	8	0.10	Off														
11:15:00	4	0.13	Off														

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B174

Date: 15/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:20:00	10	0.14	0	1	1												
11:22:00	500	0.13	6	100	100	100	800	1000	2000				2000		8		
11:25:00	15	0.12		2	1			15									
11:30:00	15	0.13	7	5	1	1	800	25	1200								
11:35:00	10	0.08		2	1			75									
11:40:00	5	0.08		400	3000	200	800	17000	1200			0.01	2000		8		
11:45:00	10	0.08	57														
11:50:00	6	0.08															
11:55:00	10	0.08		2	1												
12:00:00	10	0.11															
12:05:00	10	0.08		2	10			25									
12:05:55	10	0.08		2	10											End of Run 2 & Start Profile 6 from FL220	
12:07:12	10	0.09														FL210	
12:08:07	10	0.09														FL200	
12:09:10	20	0.13														FL190	
12:10:06	15	0.11														FL180	
12:11:01	12	0.09		1												FL170	
12:12:06	7	0.10														FL160	
12:13:06	12	0.11														FL150	
12:14:00	5	0.13														FL140	
12:15:00	85	0.11		2	1											FL130	
12:16:09	160	0.10		5	1											FL120	
12:17:00	500	0.10		10	3											FL110	
12:17:45	550	0.10		10	3											FL100	
12:18:45	1000	0.10		20	3											FL090	
12:19:39	1100	0.11		20	3											FL080	
12:20:30	790	0.10		20	2											FL070	
12:21:34	735	0.10		15	2											FL060	
12:22:30	340	0.10		10	2											FL050	
12:23:37	1400	0.08		10	2											FL040	
12:25:46	80	0.10		10	2											FL030	
12:27:41	160	0.10	58	30	3											FL020	
12:29:51	350	0.10	Off	80	10											FL010	
12:33:20	500	0.11	Off	200	15											End of Profile 6 & Start Profile 7 @ 50'	
12:34:29																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 3.1 @ 500'	
12:35:00	420	0.11	Off	100	10												
12:37:00	410	0.11	Off	100	12												
12:39:00	430	0.11	Off	100	10												
12:40:15																End of Run 3.1 @ 500'	
12:42:25																Start Run 3.2 @ 500'	
12:43:00	400	0.11	Off	100	10												
12:45:00	420	0.11	Off	100	15												
12:47:00	430	0.11	Off	100	15												
12:49:00	400	0.10	Off	100	10												
12:51:00	380	0.11	Off	80	10												
12:53:00	340	0.11	Off	80	10												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B174

Date: 15/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:55:00	360	0.10	Off	80	5												
12:57:00	420	0.10	Off	80	5												
12:59:00	450	0.09	Off	70	5												
13:00:05																End of Run 3.2	
13:02:40																Start Run 4.1 @ 100	
13:03:00	460	0.10	Off	80	7												
13:05:00	410	0.10	Off	80	7												
13:07:00	400	0.10	Off	90	9												
13:09:00	410	0.10	Off	100	10												
13:11:00	500	0.11	Off	130	10												
13:13:00	460	0.10	Off	120	10												
13:14:59																End of Run 4.1	
13:16:12																Start Run 4.2 @ 100'	
13:17:00	450	0.11	Off	110	10												
13:19:00	500	0.10	Off	120	10												
13:21:00	500	0.10	Off	120	10												
13:23:00	465	0.10	Off	100	5												
13:23:38																End of Run 4.2	
13:24:57																Start Run 4.3 @ 100'	
13:25:00	450	0.10	Off	100	10												
13:27:00	460	0.10	Off	100	10												
13:28:55																End of Run 4.3	
13:30:31																Start Run 4.4 @ 100'	
13:31:00	425	0.11	Off	100	10												
13:33:00	450	0.10	Off	100	10												
13:35:36																End of Run 4.4	
13:36:53																Start Run 4.5 @ 100'	
13:37:00	450	0.10	Off	100	10												
13:39:00	520	0.10	Off	100	10												
13:41:00	500	0.10	Off	100	9												
13:43:05																End of Run 4.5	
13:43:46	520	0.10	Off	90	10											Start Profile 8 from 100'	
13:44:45	330	0.10	Off	70	9											FL010	
13:45:52	120	0.10	Off	20	3											FL020	
13:45:54	90	0.09	Off	10	2											FL030	
13:48:04	600	0.08	Off	10	2											FL040	
13:49:08	100	0.09	Off	5	1											FL050	
13:50:10	400	0.09	Off	5	1											FL060	
13:51:06	670	0.10	Off	5	1											FL070	
13:52:11	750	0.10	Off	5	1											FL080	
13:53:14	510	0.10	Off	5	2											FL090	
13:54:10	390	0.10	Off	5	2											FL100	
13:55:10	450	0.10	Off	5	2											FL110	
13:56:23	260	0.10	Off	5	2											FL120	
13:57:17	65	0.09	Off	1	1											End of Profile 8 @ FL130	
14:00:00																Start Profile 9 from FL130	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B174****Date:**

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC	X	
Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data	X	
Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	X	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory	X	
PMSDATA: on FLOODS	X	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS	X	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
c) Output directory: PMSDATA:	X	
d) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
e) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT	X	Note the calibration file used
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) TAS in processing: Y	X	
d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0	X	
e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file.	X	Zero glitches
Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt	X	Cal27022006.txt
Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	X	
f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N	X	Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	X	No time offset
5) In PVWAVE	X	
a) enter:	X	
!path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat',	X	
'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto	X	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
1st argument is output file from 5)	X	20 seconds !!
2nd argument is the MFD	X	
3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format	X	
c) exit		
6) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp	X	
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name	X	MFDC
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	yes	Only a few cloud penetrations
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B174

Date:

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	Condor
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	37706 blocks written
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	X	Zero bad blocks
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10		
iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	X	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) File generation: Hit enter	X	
d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	X	092400 z start time chosen
e) TAS: Y	X	
f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty	X	
h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	X	
k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown	X X X	Note the particle type: 8
l) Coefficient choice: 2	X	2
m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	X	B174_PROC2D
10) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'	X	
iii) exit	X	
11) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D	X	
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	MFDD
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?	yes	For what cloud data there is...

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B174

Date:

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	Note the volume flow rate
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	X	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	X	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1	X	Bin 1 chosen
If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	X X	
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value.	X	
Calibration files to be stored in ?????	X	
Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm3/sec	X	1.6 ml/sec
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	X	
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat'	X	
'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	MFDE
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B174

Date:

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
- stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary				

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** Bnnn**Date:** DD/MM/YY

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
- rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B174

Date:

15 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 μm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B174Q4	----	----	Top	10:48:24	11:00:16	R1	1525	Run cut short
Filters run1	B174N3	----	----	Bottom	10:48:24	11:00:16	R1	1044	Run cut short
Filters run2	B174Q5	----	----	Top	12:34:25	13:00:04	R3.1/R3.2	3784	R3.1 = 0.50–0.53 kft R3.2 = 0.55–0.62 kft Turn in between
Filters run2	B174N9	----	----	Bottom	12:34:25	13:00:04	R3.1/R3.2	2557	R3.1 = 0.50–0.53 kft R3.2 = 0.55–0.62 kft Turn in between
Filters run3	B174Q8	----	----	Top	13:03:48	13:16:58	R4.1	1553	0.17–0.16 kft
Filters run3	B174N6	----	----	Bottom	13:03:48	13:16:58	R4.1	1000	0.17–0.16 kft
Filters run4	B174Q7	----	----	Top	13:20:01	13:29:30	R4.2/R4.3	1273	R4.2 = 0.15–0.20 kft R4.3 = 0.14–0.25 kft
Filters run4	B174N10	----	----	Bottom	13:20:01	13:29:30	R4.2/R4.3	820	R4.2 = 0.15–0.20 kft R4.3 = 0.14–0.25 kft
Filters run5	B174Q6	----	----	Top	13:32:58	13:43:05	R4.4/R4.5	1534	R4.4 = 0.17–0.18 kft R4.5 = 0.18 kft
Filters run5	B174N4	----	----	Bottom	13:32:58	13:43:05	R4.4/R4.5	898	R4.4 = 0.17–0.18 kft R4.5 = 0.18 kft

ARIES flight log

Flight: B174

Location: S. Mauritania, then S. of Dakar.

page 1 of 2

Date: 15-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution:

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
092750	pan	B174 4							— extra/	flight ID error.
0944	T/O (Software reinstalled)									
094811	P1	B174B	C	75	26	21	-190	27	CH1x1	OK
095112	"	B174C	C	71	31	21	-190	27	CH2x1	OK
095500	"	B174D	C	71	31	22	-190	27	N1x1	OK
095620	"	B174E	C	71	31	22	-190	27	Z1x1	OK
095731	"	B174F	C	71	31	22	-190	27	1Rx1	OK
104550	R1, 4500'	B174G	C	71	31	20	-190	27	CH1x2	OK
104805	"	B174H	O	71	31	20	-190	26	Z1x5	OK
105308?	"	B174I	¹⁰ /C	71	31	19	-190	25	CH1x2	OK
105512	"	B174J	O	71	71	19	-190	25	Z1x5	OK
101110	ER1	B174K	C	71	31	19	-190	25	CH1x1	OK
123426	R2, 1500'	B174L	OC	71	31	20	-190	-23	CH1x1	OK
1236	" 500'	B174M	O	71	31	23	-190	24	Z1x5	OK EOR & turn
124231	R3, 2 "	N	C	71	32	23	-190	25	CH1x1	OK
1244 ^N	"	O	O	71	32	24	-190	25	Z1x5	OK
124825	P1 "	P	C	70	33	25	-190	25	CH1x1	
125440	"	Q	^C /O	71	33	25	-190	25	Z1x5	Vanceley 1 GMS
↳	"	R	C	71	34	26	-189.9	26	CH1x1	OK

ARIES flight log

Flight: B174

Location: Senegal

page 2 of 2

Date: 15-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
12592	R3.2	B174S	c	71	41	27	-190	27	CH1X1	OK
120254	R4.100	B174U	c	70	39	27	-190	27	CH1X1	OK
120408	"	B174V	c	71	39	27	-190	29	N1X4	some weird / GMS on save screen
130825	"	B174W	c	71	39	27	-190	28	CH1X1	} OK
130925	"	B174X	o	71	39	27	-190	28	Z1X5	
131404	"	B174Y	o/c	71	40	28	-190	28	CH1X1	
131523	*Turn	B174Z	c			ok			CH1X1	
	R4.2	∅	o			ok			Z1X5	
132116	"	1	c						CH1X1	
132249	"	2	o	71	42	27	-191	28	Z1X5	EOR 132329 / OK
132520	R4.3	3	c			ok			CH1X1	OK
132640	"	4	o			ok			Z1X5	EOR + turn 1329 /
133122	"	5	c						CH1X1	OK
133235	"	6	c/o			ok			Z1X5	EOR + turn 1335 / OK
133711		7	o/c			ok			CH1X1	} OK
133830		8	o						Z1X1	
134312		9	c						CH1X1	

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B174	Date	15/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	1
Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS									
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0847						Rack pc time set, time server u/s?			
0848						Laptop time set			
All SWS and SHIMS modules ok on start up (box temp =15...!), but SHIMS nir shutter u/s. SHIMS operated from laptop, SWS from rack pc									
094402	P1					T/o Dakar			
095559	P1		Zen+6 fwd	200	500	All recording ok now	x		
0956	P1			100	500			x	
095845						All shutters closed for 15s			
100013	P1	FL130				End profile, shutters closed			
100154						Restart recording, integ times changed			
100325	P2	FL130	Zen +6fwd	100	500	Start profile down, cloud above	X		
1003				75	250			x	
102118	P3	50'				End profile, start next			
102947		FL50				End profile, shutters closed			
103706	P4	FL50				Start profile down			
104103		3000'				End profile, no dust, shutters closed			
104303	P5	3000'				Start profile			
104534	R1	FL045				End profile, start run, cloud above			
1054	R1	FL045	Zen+6 fwd	100	500	Ci above	X		
1054	R1	FL045		75	250			X	
105715						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp = 18, some thin Ci above			
110017		FL045				End run, close shutters, box temp = 19			
111039	R2	FL220				Start run, mostly clear above, box temp =20			
1115						Thick Ci above			
1121						In/out cloud			
112727	R2	FL220	Zen+6 fwd	50	500	Changed SWS integ time	x		
1127				75	250			X	
1139						In/out cloud			
114730						Shutters closed for 15s			
120555	P6	FL220				Start profile down, cloud above, going into biomass haze layer			
123323	P7	50'				End profile, shutters closed, start next			
123425	R3.1	500'				End profile, start run, cloud above			
124013						End run, shutters closed			
124226	R3.2	500'				Start run			
1243			Zen+6 fwd	50	500	In haze layer, some cloud above, box temp = 17	X		
1243	R3.2	500'		75	250			X	
1247						SHIMS nir dropped out, box temp = 18			
124845	R3.2	500'		75	250	SHIMS restarted		X	
130004						End run, shutters closed, box = 17			
130243	R4	100'	Nad+6 aft	50	500	Start run, view of sea, clear above initially, Ci later on in run	x		

WAS Filling Log			
Operator - Jim McQuaid			
Date	Bottle#	Start	End
15/02/2006	22	12:43:25	12:44:25
15/02/2006	23	12:48:18	12:49:18
15/02/2006	24	12:50:26	12:51:26
15/02/2006	1	12:56:27	12:57:27
15/02/2006	2	12:58:35	12:59:35
15/02/2006	3	13:04:06	13:05:06
15/02/2006	4	13:08:35	13:09:35
15/02/2006	5	13:17:11	13:18:11
15/02/2006	6	13:25:35	13:26:35
15/02/2006	7	13:32:51	13:33:51
15/02/2006	8	13:35:03	13:36:03
15/02/2006	9	13:39:53	13:40:53
15/02/2006	10	13:41:57	13:42:57

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 174 Date: 15th February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	Y	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	Y

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B174

Date: 15 February 2006

Instruments

1. JW not operated
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B174:

Log	Reason
CCN	No log was taken/is available for CCN.
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC
PAN	No log is taken/provided for PAN

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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